

Skills 4 eosc

D1.3 Data Management Plan – final version

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable is the third version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Skills4EOSC project, delivered in M36. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the Embedding Open Science in the Skills4EOSC Methodology section.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and used, and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the Horizon Europe DMP template.

Sara Di Giorgio (GARR) acts as the data manager in the Skills4EOSC project and is in charge of the actions described by this DMP. She took over this role from Emma Lazzeri (GARR) in May 2024.

The Skills4EOSC project has implemented various strategies to align with Open Science and FAIR principles. These strategies are reflected in the DMP and in the Skills4EOSC Starter Kit, a reference document on project management procedures that is available to all project participants.

1.2 Data summary

Table 1 presents an overview of datasets that were created within the project. It is based on the analysis of outputs of all work packages. The online tools used to collect survey data during the project are specified in Section 1.3. Detailed information on the [Skills4EOSC Moodle learning platform](#)¹ that was used for training and gathering feedback can be found in Section 7.

A subset of data that may be relevant to everyone interested in EOSC, its activities, and beyond, was published together with the project's deliverables, reports, and presentations in the [Skills4EOSC community space in Zenodo](#)² (see Table 2).

¹ <https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/>

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/skills4eosC/records>

Table 1 - Produced datasets.

dataset ID	title	type	format	contains sensitive data
<i>P1</i>	Deliverables and reports	Standard office documents	PDF, PPTX, DOCX, XLSX	no
<i>P2</i>	Administrative data for the project	Structured text	CSV	yes
<i>P3</i>	List of RDM training resources	Structured text	CSV	no
<i>P4</i>	List of reference sources for minimum viable skillset properties	Structured text	CSV	no
<i>P5</i>	Events video recordings	Audio-visual data	MP4	no
<i>P6</i>	Overview of Results in TtT Evaluation & Feedback	Standard office document	ELSX	no
<i>P7</i>	Participants information	Standard office documents	CSV	yes
<i>P8</i>	Participating institutions information	Standard office documents	CSV	yes
<i>P9</i>	Presentations given for the project	Standard office documents	PDF	no
<i>P10</i>	Mapping of existing professional networks: Reference data and documentation	Standard office documents	XLSX, PDF	no
<i>P11</i>	CC and USC landscaping results	Standard office documents	XLSX	no
<i>P12</i>	Open Science interview	Audio-visual data	MP4	no

	series			
P13	Science4Policy Kit - Survey Responses	Standard office documents	CSV	yes
P14	Quality Assurance Framework Description	Standard office document	XLSX	no
P15	Advocacy Kit recordings	Audio-visual data	MP4	yes
P16	Booklet series to present the key outcomes of the project	PDF documents	PDF	no

Several tasks and activities in the project required the gathering and classification of existing materials and resources that were not produced by the project but served as sources for the work of Skills4EOSC members. These important resources were shared in a systematic way through the Skills4EOSC related Zotero Libraries and made available to the larger EOSC and Open Science community.

1.3 Tools used for data creation

1.3.1 Information regarding the evaluation & feedback spreadsheets (T2.4: P9)

As part of the implementation and validation of the Skill4EOSC Quality Assurance Framework (QAF), a set of Evaluation & Feedback Spreadsheets was used to assess the quality of five pilot Train-the-Trainer (TtT) courses. These spreadsheets supported both self-assessment by course teams and external review by the T2.4 team. These are the data types collected:

- Scores assigned to each QAF indicator (per course)
- Free-text feedback and suggestions for improvement
- Course identifiers (title and link to project website's courses index)

All spreadsheet data is stored in, within restricted-access folders owned by the project coordination team. Access is limited to authorised project partners. No personal identifiers are required to complete the evaluation.

Only the Skills4EOSC Overview of Results in TtT Evaluation & Feedback (see P9 in Table 2) was published.

1.3.2 Information regarding the Skills4EOSC quality compass app

The S4E Quality Compass³ is a web-based self-assessment tool developed to support the evaluation and continuous improvement of Open Science training materials in line with the Skills4EOSC Quality Assurance Framework (QAF). The following outlines the app's data-related design, software environment, and privacy considerations:

1. Software and Technical Infrastructure

- **Framework:** The app is built using R Shiny, an open-source web application framework for R.
- **Server:** It is hosted on a university-maintained Shiny Server instance at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (UC3M).
- **Front-end:** The user interface is built using R Shiny's standard components, supporting interactive inputs and real-time outputs.
- **Data Storage:** User responses are stored in a structured format on Google Drive, accessible only to the app administrators (i.e. Developers at the UC3M).

2. Data Collection and Types

The app collects two types of information:

A. Assessment Data (Non-personal):

- Responses to QAF indicators (Yes/No/Not Applicable)
- Optional user feedback
- Section and sub-framework completion data
- Timestamp of submission

B. Optional Metadata (Personal and contextual):

- Role (e.g. course designer, trainer)
- Affiliation or institution

³ <https://csslab.uc3m.es/shiny/S4E-Quality-Compass-App/>

- Involvement in the Skills4EOSC project
- Title of the course
- Prior experience with QA processes

Providing this metadata is completely optional. All users receive their assessment results regardless of whether personal/contextual data is submitted.

3. Use of Data and Access Protocols

- **Purpose:** Data is collected exclusively for:
 - Improving the QAF and app functionality
 - Research and evaluation purposes within the Skills4EOSC project
- **Storage:** Data is stored on Google Drive in secure, access-controlled folders owned and maintained by UC3M research staff.
- **Access:** Only authorised project members from Task 2.4 have access. No data is shared externally or used for commercial purposes.

4. Privacy, Consent, and Terms of Use

The app includes a Privacy Notice and clear Terms of Use, available from the main “About” page. Users are informed that:

- No personal data is required to use the app
- Optional data is stored securely and used only for internal evaluation and research
- They may withdraw consent at any time by contacting the project team
- Upon request, submitted data will be fully deleted from all records.

The system complies with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) standards.

5. Data Retention and Reuse

Data collected will be stored securely for 10 years after the duration of the Skills4EOSC project, and anonymised for longer-term analysis if approved.

Anonymised data may be used in publications or reports, but no personal identifiers will ever be disclosed.

1.3.3 Information regarding the Advocacy Kit

The video material, which was shot and published with participants consent, was produced by Chalmers University of Technology and Università di Torino. This material was stored on Chalmers encrypted servers and a closed copy is archived there still. Moreover the transcripts were created using an AI-service hosted by Chalmers and manually reviewed before being attached to the videos.

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

We made our data findable by uploading it to a data repository (Zenodo) that provides a persistent identifier (DOI) and adding relevant metadata. The repository provides means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

We used the [Data Documentation Initiative \(DDI\)](https://ddialliance.org/)⁴ metadata standards whenever possible to document survey data. Wherever needed, we provided a README file explaining all values and terms used next to each file with data.

Additionally, we provided common metadata such as title, description, or keywords. In this case, we followed the default template provided by the Zenodo repository, which is the [DataCite metadata schema](https://schema.datacite.org/)⁵.

As far as possible, we used controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. For clear and persistent reference, we provided the data creators' ORCID iDs in Zenodo where available.

2.2 Making data accessible

We made our data accessible by providing open access to data wherever possible. In cases where open access was not possible, we provided meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Data that had to be deleted at the end of the project is described in Section 5.

We used Zenodo to publish data. Zenodo is a simple and innovative trusted service that allows researchers, scientists, EU projects, and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based

⁴ <https://ddialliance.org/>

⁵ <https://schema.datacite.org>

repositories of the research communities. Zenodo enables researchers, scientists, EU projects, and institutions to:

- easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats, including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science.
- display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission.
- easily access and reuse shared research results.

All the project outputs can be found on the [Skills4EOSC community in Zenodo](#)⁶ that is maintained by the data manager.

The repository will host the data for at least 20 years, but a longer retention period is expected. This meets our requirements.

Table 2 provides an overview of all published datasets, their location, PID, and license.

Table 2 - Overview of published datasets.

<i>dataset ID</i>	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	publication date	PID/location	license
<i>P1</i>	Open	-	diverse	DOIs, see collection in Zenodo and on the website https://www.skills4eosc.eu/resources/deliverables-milestones	CC BY 4.0
<i>P6</i>	Open	-	2025-06-29	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15766566	CC BY 4.0
<i>P9</i>	Open	-	diverse	DOIs, see collection in Zenodo	CC BY 4.0

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/skills4eosc/>

<i>P10</i>	Open	-	2023-02-01	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7591902	CC BY 4.0
<i>P11</i>	Open	-	2023-09-14	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8345511	CC BY 4.0
<i>P12</i>	Open	-	2024-01-24	DOIs, see collection in Zenodo	CC BY 4.0
<i>P13</i>	Open	was anonymised before publication	2024-12-04	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14275893	CC BY 4.0
<i>P14</i>	Open	-	2025-06-29	DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15766527	CC BY 4.0
<i>P15</i>	Open	-	2024-01-24	DOIs: 10.5281/zenodo.10564842 10.5281/zenodo.10564854 10.5281/zenodo.10564859 10.5281/zenodo.10564861 10.5281/zenodo.10564863 10.5281/zenodo.10564856 and on the website https://www.skills4eosoc.eu/resources/advocacy-kit	CC BY 4.0
<i>P16</i>	Open	-	diverse	DOIs, see collection in Zenodo and on	CC BY

				the website https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications and https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs	4.0
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P5 (Events video recordings): Video recordings of the public launch and final conference have been published on GARR TV and on the Skills4EOSC website. Other recordings are not published.

Milestones in the project were treated as short reports. They are included in P1 and were published as soon as they became available. In Zenodo, these reports are specified as “Project milestones”.

Milestone reports and public deliverables were reviewed by project partners who were not involved in creating the documents and approved by the coordinator before publication. A DOI was reserved in Zenodo and placed on the front page of the document prior to the upload. As a measure to support co-creation and enhance reproducibility, public milestones and deliverables were published as soon as possible, even in draft versions. Updated documents were later added as new versions to the existing records, followed by final versions at the end of the project.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Whenever possible, we followed standards such as DDI or DataCite to foster interoperability of data. As far as possible, we used controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We ensured good documentation of our datasets and provided README files in addition to a clear description in Zenodo wherever needed to inform about methods used for collecting or generating the data, data specific parameters, etc.

2.4 Increase data re-use

We made our data reusable by adding metadata to all published datasets and comprehensive README files where needed. The descriptions and documentation associated with the project results include details on the methodology used and analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data were always assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained were published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there were no data protection concerns (see Table 2).

We used consistent and meaningful file names that reflect the file content and file formats that are recommended for long-term preservation.

3 Other research outputs

One of the project's key outputs is learning materials produced by WP3-6 targeting different stakeholders. The design of Skills4EOSC materials is based on the core deliverable [D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials](#)⁷. The methodology is a result of task 2.3, which passed a co-design process engaging the Skills4EOSC participants and the larger EOSC community via specific a consultation mechanism. It was published in Zenodo in M12.

The methodology includes specification for metadata schema and repositories to be used, processes to ensure the material is in line with the FAIR principles, and thus fully reusable by both trainers and trainees, as well as a mechanism to assess the quality of the material itself.

⁷ Filiposka, S., Green, D., Mishev, A., Kjorveziroski, V., Corleto, A., Napolitano, E., Paolini, G., Di Giorgio, S., Janik, J., Schirru, L., Gingold, A., Hadrossek, C., Souyioultzoglou, I., Leister, C., Pavone, G., Sharma, S., Mendez Rodriguez, E. M., & Lazzeri, E. (2023). D2.2 Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Training Materials (1.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305540>

4 Allocation of resources

The data manager directed the data management process overall, with the work package leaders being responsible for ensuring that metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up, and other quality control activities were maintained. The researcher were be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

The costs of data management were all staff costs and accounted for.

5 Data security

For the duration of the project, the data manager ensured safe storage and backup of data. During the project, data was stored in **workplace.skills4eosc.eu** with limited access to people involved in the given WP. The service was hosted in Italy by GARR. It is GDPR compliant, and the data was backed-up.

We paid strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. In this project, there were sensitive data in datasets P2 (Administrative data for the project), P7 (Participants information), P8 (Participating institutions information), P13 (Science4Policy Kit - Survey Responses) and P15 (Advocacy Kit recordings). To ensure that the storage and transfer of sensitive data was safe, additional security measures such as individual log-in and password were taken. Only selected work package members were authorised to access sensitive data.

In this project, we processed personal data: P2 (Administrative data for the project), P7 (Participants information), P8 (Participating institutions information), P13 (Science4Policy Kit - Survey Responses) and P15 (Advocacy Kit recordings) contained personal data (see Table 1). To ensure compliance with data protection laws, informed consent for processing personal data and pseudonymisation of personal data was gained. This includes informed consent for the publication of the master trainer's bios and photos on the website.

Table 3 - Access control rights for datasets during the project.

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
<i>P1</i>	writing	writing	no access
<i>P2</i>	writing	no access	no access
<i>P3</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P4</i>	writing	reading only	no access

<i>P5</i>	writing	no access	no access
<i>P6</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P7</i>	writing	no access	no access
<i>P8</i>	writing	no access	no access
<i>P9</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P10</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P11</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P12</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P13</i>	writing	no access	no access
<i>P14</i>	writing	reading only	no access
<i>P15</i>	recording	no access	no access
<i>P16</i>	writing	reading only	no access

All incidents were handled individually by an incident response team that was responsible for the affected service.

Not all of the datasets could be published at the end of the project. Table 4 lists datasets that had to be deleted.

Table 4 - Deleted datasets.

<i>kind/name of data</i>	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person
<i>P7</i>	2025-08-30	Includes personal data	Data Manager
<i>P8</i>	2025-08-30	Includes personal data	Data Manager

6 ELSI

Skills4EOSC took into account the Ethical, Legal and Social Issues in the project activities in its ELSI meta work package, which is transversal in the methodology. As ELSI were embedded throughout the activities of all work packages as transversal elements, one task from the ELSI Meta-WP was included in all relevant work packages (WP2, 3.4 and 5).

The ELSI related project activities included discussion on the following aspects:

- Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)
- Public Sector Information (PSI)
- Open Data
- licensing
- database rights
- integrity
- responsible and participatory research
- impact on society

In particular, the ELSI aspects were discussed in WP3 to cover the science for policy interface and in WP5, addressing the different needs of the various research communities and the accessibility of the various types of data they produce.

These discussions addressed the balance between sharing research results under the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” and the ethical impact on involved communities and individuals, as well as the legal aspects deriving from mandates and regulations, policies and legislative interventions at all levels.

7 Skills4EOSC Moodle Platform

7.1 Tools used for data creation

Skills4EOSC uses the [Moodle learning platform](#)⁸ as part of its training services for relevant stakeholders training activities. Detailed information about the use of collected data can be found in the [privacy policy](#)⁹.

7.1.1 Software and Technical Infrastructure

Framework: Moodle Learning Management System (LMS) - Version 4.1.18

Server: The Moodle instance used by Skills4EOSC is maintained and managed by GARR. The instance and all its third-party plugins are hosted on GARR web servers.

Front-end: Web-based interface accessible via <https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/>

Data Storage: Database management system hosted on GARR's institutional servers with integrated third-party plugins.

7.1.2 Data Collection and Types

The platform collects the following types of data:

User Profile Data:

- User ID
- Name and Surname
- Email address
- Username
- Moodle role designation

Activity Logs:

- IP address

⁸ <https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/>

⁹

<https://learning.skills4eosC.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php?returnurl=https%3A%2F%2Flearning.skills4eosC.eu%2F%3Fredirect%3D0>

- User ID
- Moodle Course ID
- Time stamp of activity
- Action type
- Moodle object interactions (e.g., Quiz, Assignment)

Training Content Data:

- Course enrolment records
- Assessment results and feedback
- Student progress tracking
- Communication records between trainers and learners

Third-party Integration Data:

- BigBlueButton webinar data including full name, IP address and meeting ID
- Session cookies for authentication and navigation

7.1.3 Use of Data and Access Protocols

Purpose:

- Provide access to the learning platform
- Deliver online training services
- Track student progress and performance
- Enable communication between teachers and learners
- Compile statistical reports about training events (in anonymized format)

Storage:

- Data is stored on GARR's institutional web servers
- Database includes user profiles, activity logs, and assessment records
- Session data managed through secure cookie mechanisms

Access:

- Course administrators have access to Moodle reports for monitoring training activity
- GARR IT administration staff may access the database for support or investigation purposes

- Trainers can access progress reports and communication tools for their assigned courses

7.1.4 Privacy, Consent, and Terms of Use

Legal Framework:

The Skills4EOSC project is bound by the European Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR)

Data Controller: GARR

Legal Basis:

All personal data stored and used is necessary for the legitimate interest of the service provider in ensuring the security of the platform for all users and in fulfilling the contractual obligations of the Skills4EOSC project in the area of training material production and training services

User Rights:

- Right to request access to personal data
- Right to request correction of personal data
- Right to request erasure of personal data
- Right to object to processing of personal data
- Right to request restriction of processing
- Right to request data transfer
- Right to withdraw consent

Data Sharing:

- GARR and Skills4EOSC do not provide users information to third parties
- Information will not be sold, exchanged, transferred, or given to third parties without consent
- Email addresses may be used for course-related communications and Skills4EOSC updates

7.1.5 Data Retention and Reuse

Retention Period:

- Personal data will be kept for no longer than 6 months after the project ends

Data Security:

- Physical, electronic, and managerial safeguards implemented
- Moodle also has safeguards in place following established security procedures
- Regular monitoring and access controls for unauthorized access prevention

Statistical Use:

- All processed data will be published in a summarized fashion, completely anonymized
- Anonymized data may be used for research and reporting purposes
- No individual identification possible in published statistics

Cookie Management:

- Session cookies (PHPSESSID, MoodleSession) for platform functionality
- Persistent cookies (MOODLEID) for user convenience
- BigBlueButton session cookies for webinar functionality
- Users can manage cookie preferences through browser settings

During the implementation of the training courses/learning paths, certain personal data of participants were collected and processed to support course delivery, communication, collaboration, and transparency, as mentioned also in the Learning Platform Privacy Policy above.

Participants' names and email addresses (as well as username, Moodle role, country, course participations, gained badges) were visible within the learning platform and accessible to other participants enrolled in the same course/learning path. This aimed to enable communication, collaboration and community building among participants, as well as trainers/course organisers, ensuring effective interaction and fostering a collaborative

learning environment, as well as transparency in the context of shared learning activities and communications.

Furthermore, names, email addresses, institutional affiliations, and countries were included in the internal project workplace. This information was used for organisational and reporting purposes, such as grouping participants per course or learning path, managing access and participation, as well as demographic analysis for the training reports.

During live sessions, Google Docs were used to facilitate communication and collaborative work. Participants were invited — but not required — to include their name, email, and institution in the shared documents to support live collaboration and networking. All Google Docs will be deleted at the end of the project.

Finally, as part of the feedback process at the end of each course/learning path, participants were invited to submit their responses through anonymous questionnaires, within the learning platform. At the end of these forms, they were optionally asked whether they wished to provide their email address for follow-up purposes.

8 Other issues

None.

9 References

No	Description/Link
R1	European Commission (2021). Horizon Europe (HORIZON) - Annotated Model Grant Agreement. Version 0.2, 30 November 2021. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf
R2	European Commission (2022a). Horizon Europe (HORIZON) - Model Grant Agreement. Version 1.1., 15 April 2022. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/agr-contr/general-mga_horizon-euratom_en.pdf